

ECOTOURISM AREA MANAGEMENT IN NARMADA DISTRICT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16268664>

Published Date: 21-July-2025

Abstract: The Sekawan Sejati area is managed separately by each village institution, meaning the areas have different functional policies due to different government involvement. However, similar tourism potential provides an opportunity for sustainable management collaboration implemented in stages. Tourism area management is determined based on tourism criteria established in the research. Direct observations and interviews were conducted to obtain scores for the existing sub-criteria. The established policies were obtained through in-depth interviews with authorities such as the Rinjani Barat Forest Management Unit (KPH) and the Nuraksa Forest Park (Tahura Nuraksa). The results of the study indicate that ecotourism management is regulated based on six policies from the Minister of Environment and Forestry and the West Lombok Regency government policies, which serve as guidelines for the Sekawan Sejati ecotourism management. Area management is divided into three aspects: economic, environmental, and social. Based on these aspects, four management indicators were obtained: tourist attractions, human resources, institutions, and other supporting services.

Keywords: Attraction, Human Resources, Institutions, Other Supporting Services.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has 1,128 ethnic groups that create cultural diversity such as dances, musical instruments, types of food, and customs that have the potential to become cultural tourism attractions. Meanwhile, Indonesia's natural attractions consist of volcanoes, seas, and flora and fauna spread across its land and seas (Rahma, 2020). In accordance with the Decree of the Governor of West Nusa Tenggara in 2019 concerning the Determination of 99 Tourist Village Locations in West Nusa Tenggara Province for 2019-2023, the tourism sector is a driver of the community's economy and is expected to run sustainably. This is because tourism activities can increase demand for consumption and investment, which leads to the emergence of production activities for goods and services. Therefore, tourism is one of the sectors that plays a role in the development and development of regions, as well as economic growth (Ardiansyah and Iskandar, 2022).

Ecotourism is managed based on the principles of environmental sustainability, while ecotourism products are developed according to the distinctive characteristics that define them (Ardiansyah and Iskandar, 2022). Tourism villages are an alternative for sustainable ecotourism development that prioritizes local communities as tourism actors. The primary attraction of a village lies in the behavior of its residents, influenced by economic, physical, and social activities in the village, such as culture, agricultural activities, natural landscapes, services, historical and cultural tourism, and unique experiences that characterize tourism villages (Triyono, 2020).

The Sekawan Sejati area is a tourist area located in Narmada District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province. The Sekawan Sejati area was inaugurated by the Deputy Governor of West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) in 2020 as a tourist attraction with great potential to become a national destination. The Sekawan Sejati area has attractions in the form of natural tourism attractions, man-made tourism, and diverse cultural tourism. The Sekawan Sejati area is managed separately by each village institution, meaning that the areas have different functional policies due to different government involvement. Based on a statement from the West Rinjani KHPL, administratively, Buwun Sejati Village and Sesaot Village are protected forest areas directly supervised by the West Rinjani KPHL. Meanwhile, Pakuan Village is a conservation forest area supervised by the Nuraksa Tahura.

Given the differences in policies and management, as well as the challenges faced by ecotourism managers in the Sekawan Sejati area, a policy analysis is needed to improve tourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area. Therefore, this study aims to identify ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Material

1. Definition and Elements of Tourism

Tourism is an activity in the form of travel carried out by people or groups outside their place of residence or environment for a period of no more than one consecutive year and has the aim of traveling, business, or other purposes without carrying out work activities while at the destination (Wirawan *et al.*, 2022). Tourism is a social, cultural, and economic phenomenon that involves the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/professional purposes (Dewitinalah, 2021). Therefore, tourism in this study is explained as an industry carried out by humans to spend time visiting interesting places in terms of natural beauty, culture, community traditions, food, and environmental education that can increase employment opportunities and the local economy.

Tourism elements are a collection of aspects that support the attractiveness and ease of travel. Because tourism development requires support, planning is necessary that reflects the tourism industry, environmental carrying capacity (natural resources), and the local community. The elements in developing a tourist village can be measured by attractions, supporting facilities, accessibility, and additional services. The study explains that the elements of attractions and additional services offered to tourists are the most important elements in developing a tourist village. Meanwhile, elements such as supporting facilities and accessibility are elements that complement the needs of tourists (Istiawan and Nugraha, 2022). Meanwhile, research conducted by Juneadet *al*(2021) recommends seven (7) elements in developing creative ecotourism. These elements include: 1) location and tourist attractions, 2) accessibility, 3) accommodation, 4) facilities, 5) tourism activities, 6) management, and 7) community participation. Therefore, the tourism aspects in this study are divided into four (4): tourist attractions, human resources, institutions, and other supporting services.

2. Definition, Principles of Ecotourism, and Ecotourism Management in Indonesia

Ecotourism encompasses three important aspects: ecological sustainability, economic sustainability, and psychological acceptability within the community. This means that ecotourism activities are carried out to obtain information with the aim of seeing, understanding, and experiencing nature intellectually and culturally. Ecotourism is inseparable from conservation, so ecotourism activities focus on developing and managing natural tourism areas and providing sales revenue and income opportunities for the Indonesian people (Maaket *al*, 2022). Ecotourism prioritizes socio-cultural empowerment, local economic development, nature conservation, and education. Therefore, ecotourism is an activity that involves visiting interesting places that can increase knowledge, is carried out responsibly towards environmental and socio-cultural sustainability, and provides a positive economic impact on the community.

Ecotourism principles according to Maak *et al* (2022) as follows:

1. Conservation Principles

The principles of conservation ecotourism are divided into two, namely: 1) nature conservation which implements responsible behavior and is committed to nature conservation and ecological development, and 2) cultural conservation is carried out to maintain local social, cultural and religious values and maintain traditions that are characteristic of an area and memorable for visiting tourists.

2. Principle of Community Participation

Communities are a crucial component in ecotourism management, as they implement policies, maintain the tourism environment, and enjoy ecotourism products. Therefore, a forum for discussion with the community is needed to formulate, plan, and implement local socio-cultural and religious preservation.

3. Economic Principles

Ecotourism activities must be able to provide benefits to the lives of local communities so that they become drivers of economic activities that can support regional economic development by applying environmental conservation principles to optimize benefits in a sustainable manner.

4. Principles of Education

Ecotourism development provides education to tourists and the community on how to improve the welfare of the community by utilizing natural potential based on the principles of environmental, socio-cultural and religious preservation of the local community.

5. Principles of tourism

Travel should create a sense of safety and comfort, while providing a satisfying and memorable experience. This will encourage tourists to return or stay longer to enjoy and achieve the desired travel experience.

Management is the activity of formulating policies to provide oversight of all aspects involved in the implementation and achievement of objectives (Nadzifah, 2020). Therefore, the management referred to in this study is a systematic effort undertaken by an individual or group to focus on strategies to achieve desired objectives through the processes of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling. Ecotourism management is an effort to strengthen the potential of the region and local community while minimizing weaknesses. Therefore, in this study, ecotourism management refers to the policies applicable to ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area, which consists of Buwun Sejati Village, Sesaot Village, and Pakuan Village (Adiiet *al.*, 2023).

2. Method

The research method used is qualitative descriptive research. The unit of analysis for this study is the management and government parties involved in developing ecotourism in the Sekawan Sejati area. The research area was determined by *purposive sampling* namely in Buwun Sejati Village, Sesaot Village, and Pakuan Village. The research respondents were determined using the method *purposive sampling*. The sample consisted of 29 people. The data types used were qualitative and quantitative. The data sources were primary and secondary data. Data collection was conducted through observation, interviews, and documentation.

The data analysis used is as follows.

Highest Score = item x Skor max

Highest Score = 40 x 4

Highest Score = 160

Lowest Score = item x Min score value

Lowest Score = 40 x 1

Lowest Score = 40

IS = Sum of Max Score - Sum of Min Score / Number of Categories

IS = 160 - 40

IS = 120

IS = 30

Table 1: Ecotourism Management Criteria

Interval	Category
40 – 70	Strongly disagree
71 – 101	Don't agree
102 – 132	Agree
133 – 160	Strongly agree

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

West Lombok Regency is the administrative center, bordering the Indian Ocean to the south, the Lombok Strait and Mataram City to the west, Central Lombok Regency to the east, and North Lombok Regency to the north. Narmada District is known as a mountainous and hilly area with an area of 112.77 km². The Sekawan Sejati area is a natural tourism area consisting of three villages: Buwun Sejati, Sesaot, and Pakuan. Buwun Sejati and Sesaot are designated as Pioneer Tourism Villages. *File Project* for West Lombok (Pesona Indonesia, 2022). Meanwhile, Pakuan Village is preparing the requirements to obtain the ADWI Village designation, organized by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy.

The tourist areas that are developing in the Sekawan Sejati area are as follows:

Table 2: List of Tourist Attractions in Sekawan Sejati

No	Name of Tourist Attraction	Tourist Attractions	Tourist Activities
1	Sesaot Tourism Forest	Protected forest	Champing
2	Sesaot	Clear Spring	Sightseeing
3	Sesaot Village	Natural beauty	Photography
4	Aik Nyet	Protected forest	Relax
5	Bunut Ngengkang	Clear Spring	Relax
6	Bawaq Are Sesaot	River flow	Relax
7	Segenter Waterfall	Waterfall	Relax
8	Batu Santek Waterfall	Waterfall	Relax
9	Chinese mosque	Chinese-style prayer room	Photography / Worship

Source: MCSTO University of Mataram, 2020

Management is a systematic effort carried out by an individual or group to focus on strategies in achieving desired goals through planning, organizing, directing, and controlling. Ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati Area refers to the policies in force from the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH) and the Nuraksa Forest Management Center (Balai Tahura Nuraksa). The Sekawan Sejati Area consists of three villages with similar tourism potential and are located close together, consisting of Buwun Sejati Village, Sesaot Village, and Pakuan Village. These villages have similar tourism potential because they are located in conservation and protected forest areas. The protected forest and conservation forest areas are managed by the NTB Province Environment and Forestry Service, specifically the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH) and the Nuraksa Forest Management Center, as well as the West Lombok Regency Tourism Office.

The differences in regulations in each area do not eliminate the role and involvement of local communities in utilizing their natural resources by managing forest products and natural resources for tourism. Local economic activities are linked to the regulations of the management, so each party has its own rules for managing the area, in accordance with the regulations of the Minister of Environment and Forestry. These regulations are presented in the following table.

All applicable regulations underlie the tourism business activities available in Sekawan Sejati and are a regional resource managed by the West Lombok Regency government. The implementation of regency-based programs is separate from that of the provincial government due to differing budgets outlined in each regional development plan. Therefore, the programs most relevant to ecotourism management are collaborations with external agencies through community service activities. Therefore, the regulations applicable to the Sekawan Sejati area serve as guidelines for management in utilizing natural resources based on ecotourism principles.

Ecotourism Management from the West Lombok Tourism Office, West Rinjani Forest Management Unit, and Nuraksa Nature Reserve

The Tourism Office is focusing on developing tourist attractions, digital promotion, human resource training, and enhancing collaboration between stakeholders. Meanwhile, the West Rinjani Forest Management Agency (KPHL) is promoting the use of protected forests for nature tourism services through legal partnerships. Nuraksa Nature Reserve (Tahura Nuraksa) has established business permit-based regulations for conservation areas such as Pakuan Village. The role of local communities as economic actors is evident in the management of non-timber forest products, culinary specialties, and even the management of parking and tourist facilities.

Ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area is carried out based on policies from the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH) and the Nuraksa Forest Park (Tahura) Office. This area encompasses three villages: Buwun Sejati, Sesaot, and Pakuan, which share similar tourism potential due to their location within protected forest and conservation areas. Management is carried out by the NTB Provincial Environment and Forestry Service.

Buwun Sejati and Sesaot villages are managed by the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH) as protected forest areas, while Pakuan Village is managed by the Nuraksa Forest Conservation Area (Tahura Nuraksa) as a conservation area. Despite differences in policies between the management agencies, the community continues to play an active role in utilizing the natural resources as a tourist destination, in accordance with regulations established by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry. Each area follows specific regulations for managing forest products and tourism.

Ecotourism Management of the Sekawan Sejati Area from the West Lombok Regency Tourism Office

The West Lombok Regency Tourism Office directs ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati Area through five main strategies:

a. Development of Tourist Attractions

The management and utilization of natural, cultural, and man-made tourist attractions are carried out by the Village-Owned Enterprises (Bumdes) and the Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) of each village. Each village boasts unique characteristics, such as Aik Nyet and art performances at Buwun Sejati, Purekmas (Community Service Center) and traditional Sasak houses in Sesaot, and waterfalls and camping areas in Pakuan. The local government is also exploring hiking trails to Mount Rinjani from this area, although no route has yet been found that lies entirely within West Lombok.

b. Digital Promotion and Marketing

Tourism destination promotion is actively carried out through social media platforms such as TikTok, YouTube, and Instagram, including local content creators. This strategy effectively expands the promotional reach and introduces new tourist locations to the public.

c. Community Empowerment and Tourism Actors

The community, which is predominantly a farmer, is involved in tourism management through partnerships with the Forest Management Unit (KPH) and the Natural Resources Conservation Agency (Tahura). Agricultural products can be sold directly to tourists. Furthermore, training for tourism practitioners is conducted on an ongoing basis and monitored by the tourism office.

d. Strengthening Collaboration and Partnership

Collaboration between the central and regional governments, the private sector, and the community is underway to increase capacity and strengthen tourism discussion forums. The three villages have also participated in national tourism village competitions to expand their networks.

e. Improving the Capacity of Civil Servants and Human Resources

Various technical training programs are held to enhance the professionalism of tourism managers, including mountain tour guides, geotourism, sanitation, outbound activities, paragliding, and diving. The training also includes the provision of facilities tailored to the needs of each type of tourism.

Ecotourism Management of the Sekawan Sejati Area from the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit

Forest management in Buwun Sejati Village and Sesaot Village by the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH) refers to the Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation No. P49/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/9/2017 concerning forest utilization cooperation within Forest Management Unit (KPH) areas. This regulation aims to strengthen sustainable forest management and encourage collaboration between KPHs and various parties such as Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), MSMEs, cooperatives, and local communities. Appropriate activities in this context include the utilization of environmental services, such as water flow utilization and nature tourism.

Several tourist attractions, such as Aik Nyet, Bunut Ngenggang, Bawaq Are, and Purekmas, are jointly managed by the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH), Village-Owned Enterprises (Bumdes), and Tourism Awareness Group

(Pokdarwis). However, not all attractions have been officially registered. For example, the Bawaq Are tourist attraction is still in its initial stages of management by local youth, despite not yet having a formal cooperation agreement. Previously neglected, this site has now developed into a clean and functional tourist attraction thanks to local initiatives.

Financial management is carried out independently to support facilities such as toilets, changing rooms, prayer rooms, and security, with an entrance fee of Rp 2,000 and parking fees of Rp 5,000 per vehicle. Meanwhile, tourist attractions registered with the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH) have official tickets ranging from Rp 5,000 to Rp 10,000 and a revenue-sharing system in accordance with Article 9 paragraph 1, namely 20% for the provincial government (first party), 75% for the management (second party), and 5% for the West Lombok Regency Government.

Ecotourism Management of the Sekawan Sejati Area from the Nuraksa Natural Park Elements

Nuraksa Tahura Center refers to PP Number 5 of 2021 concerning *Implementation of Risk-Based Business Licensing*, which requires business actors, including MSMEs, to have a Business Identification Number (NIB) and a standard business activity certificate based on the results of a risk analysis. For the tourism sector, this is explained in Article 140 concerning licensing in the tourism sector based on the activity's risk level.

In addition, Ministerial Regulation No. 3 of 2021 regulates standards for business activities in the environmental and forestry sectors, including the utilization of forest potential, waste management, environmental services, and flora/fauna conservation. Specifically in the Sekawan Sejati Area, permitted business forms include the utilization of environmental services in protected forests and conservation areas; nature tourism service businesses in conservation areas such as Grand Forest Parks; provision of micro- to large-scale water and hydropower services; and geothermal exploration and exploitation. Meanwhile, Ministerial Regulation No. P.8/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/3/2019 regulates the governance of nature tourism businesses in conservation areas such as national parks and grand forest parks. This regulation covers permit application procedures, business implementation, timeframes, guidance, evaluation, and sanctions for tourism operators.

Ecotourism Management in the Sekawan Sejati Area from Bumdes and Pokdarwis Sekawan Sejati Elements Based on Economic, Social, and Environmental Aspects

a. Economy

Local communities utilize non-timber forest products such as fruit and palm sap as a source of income. Products like palm sugar, banana chips, and local foods are sold to tourists. Furthermore, the community sells food around tourist attractions, charging a fee for cleanliness and security. This economic participation strengthens the community's role in tourism management.

b. Environment

Maintaining the cleanliness of tourist areas is a shared responsibility between managers, the community, and tourists. Area management is carried out through a collaborative scheme (in protected forests) and a partnership (in conservation forests) with the provincial government. The increasing number of tourists can potentially damage the environment if not managed properly. Therefore, controlling visitor numbers and educating about cleanliness are key priorities. If managed sustainably, this area has the potential to become an international destination and an alternative route to Mount Rinjani.

c. Social

Local communities act as hospitable hosts welcoming tourists and playing a vital role in cultural preservation. Communication between stakeholders is essential for smooth management coordination. This area has potential for cultural tourism, including: *little lady-in-waiting*, *turn around*, and the tradition of praying in caves. Government training programs aim to raise public awareness of the importance of preserving culture. However, some communities still fail to fully implement this training. Sustainable innovation will open up more economic opportunities and improve local well-being.

Ecotourism Management Calculation

Ecotourism management in Sekawan Sejati is measured based on four indicators: attractiveness, human resources, institutions, and other supporting services. The results of the calculation of ecotourism management in Sekawan Sejati using a Likert scale are explained below.

Table 3: Ecotourism Management Indicators in Sekawan Sejati

No	Variables	STS		TS		S		SS		Total	
		Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%
1	Attractiveness	1	5	2	20	15	70	3	14	21	100
2	Human Resources	1	5	4	19	13	62	3	14	21	100
3	Institutional	1	5	0	0	14	67	6	29	21	100
4	Other Support Services	1	5	4	19	14	67	2	10	21	100

Source, primary data 2024

Based on table 3, there are four variables that can be developed by managers in the Sekawan Sejati area as an ecotourism area. The attraction variable supports the management of the ecotourism area with 70% (15 people) choosing “agree” and 14% (3 people) choosing “strongly agree.” This means that the management of the tourist attractions available in Sekawan Sejati can attract tourists to come and visit. In addition to attractive tourism, the tourist location is easily accessible to local and international tourists. The human resources variable supports the management of the ecotourism area with 62% (13 people) choosing “agree” and 14% (3 people) choosing “strongly agree.” This means that the management of the human resources available in the Sekawan Sejati area can support the development of ecotourism. The institutional variable supports the management of the ecotourism area with 67% (14 people) choosing “agree” and 29% (6 people) choosing “strongly agree.” This means that ecotourism management is supported by the social system that applies in the Sekawan Sejati area. Other supporting service variables support the management of ecotourism with 67% (14 people) choosing “agree” and 10% (2 people) choosing “strongly agree.” This means that the services available support ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area.

Attractiveness

The tourist attractions of the Sekawan Sejati area are natural attractions, man-made attractions, and cultural attractions which are the destinations for tourists to visit.

Table 4: Criteria for Attractiveness Indicators

No	Criteria	Strongly Disagree		Don't agree		Agree		Strongly agree		Total	
		Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%
1	Perception of natural tourist attractions	1	5	2	10	12	57	6	29	21	100
2	Perception of artificial tourist attractions	1	5	1	5	13	62	6	29	21	100
3	Perception of artificial tourism development	1	5	3	14	14	67	3	14	21	100
4	Perception of conservation activities	1	5	4	19	12	57	4	19	21	100
5	Perception of the uniqueness of cultural tourism	1	5	4	19	10	48	6	29	21	100
6	Perception of clean and tidy tourist amenities	1	5	3	14	11	52	6	29	21	100
7	Perception of amenity availability	1	5	4	19	13	62	3	14	21	100
8	Perception of quantity of tourism facilities	1	5	5	24	15	71	0	0	21	100
9	Perception of changing room cleanliness	1	5	6	29	13	62	1	5	21	100
10	Infrastructure perception	1	5	4	19	13	62	3	14	21	100
11	Perception of means	1	5	5	24	11	52	4	19	21	100
12	Perception of tourism object development	1	5	1	5	16	76	3	14	21	100
13	Perception of cheap tour package prices	1	5	2	10	18	86	0	0	21	100
14	The perception of tour packages having clear permits	1	5	3	14	15	71	2	10	21	100

Source, primary data 2024

Based on table 6The management of the Sekawan Sejati attraction variable offers the advantage of affordable and accessible tour packages. Despite the low ticket prices, management requires a management system that pays more attention to the cleanliness of amenities and tourist facilities to ensure tourists feel comfortable and enjoy the available attractions longer.

Human Resources

Sekawan Sejati's human resources are local communities and *stakeholder* who are involved in managing tourist areas.

Table 5: Human Resource Indicator Criteria

No	Criteria	Strongly Disagree		Don't agree		Agree		Strongly agree		Total	
		Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%
1	Perception of the use of Indonesian	1	5	1	5	15	71	4	19	21	100
2	Perception of English usage	1	5	6	29	10	48	4	19	21	100
3	Perception of regional language use	1	5	2	10	13	62	5	24	21	100
4	Perception of hospitality	1	5	2	10	15	71	3	14	21	100
5	Perception of waste management	2	10	5	24	9	43	5	24	21	100
6	Perception of the availability of trash	3	14	6	29	8	38	4	19	21	100
7	Managers' knowledge perception	1	5	2	10	12	57	6	29	21	100

Source, primary data 2024

Based on Table 7, human resources in the Sekawan Sejati area have good Indonesian language skills for tourists. This facilitates further interaction with tourists and promotes the natural riches of Sekawan Sejati. Research by Istiawan and Nugraha (2022) explains that to support the development of tourist villages, community participation in welcoming tourists requires good language skills to provide comfort and facilitate information exchange.

Institutional

Institutions in the Sekawan Sejati area are structures and roles *stakeholder* who manages the Sekawan Sejati area.

Table 6: Institutional Indicator Criteria

No	Criteria	Strongly Disagree		Don't agree		Agree		Strongly agree		Total	
		Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%
1	Perception of creativity in maintaining tourism infrastructure and facilities	1	5	0	0	17	81	3	14	21	100
2	Perception of involvement <i>stakeholder</i>	1	5	1	5	17	81	2	10	21	100
3	Perception of order in policy	1	5	0	0	16	76	4	19	21	100
4	The perception is that there are policies that protect the natural wealth of tourism.	0	0	2	10	13	62	6	29	21	100
5	Perception of policy implementation by managers	1	5	1	5	16	76	3	14	21	100
6	Village profile perception	1	5	2	10	14	67	4	19	21	100
7	Perception of tourism promotion media through websites	1	5	3	14	11	52	6	29	21	100
8	Perception of tourism promotion creativity	1	5	2	10	12	57	6	29	21	100
9	Perception of providing training to MSMEs	1	5	1	5	13	62	6	29	21	100
10	Perception of the formation of MSME groups as a follow-up to training	1	5	2	10	11	52	7	33	21	100
11	Perception of ecotourism knowledge to managers	0	0	1	5	17	81	3	14	21	100
12	Perception of e-money usage	1	5	7	33	9	43	4	19	21	100
13	Tourist perception supports MSMEs using QRIS	0	0	3	14	16	76	2	10	21	100

Source, primary data 2024

Based on Table 8, the institutions involved in managing the Sekawan Sejati area are able to collaborate and create a creative environment to attract visitors without compromising existing policies. This finding is supported by Maak's research *et al* (2022) which explains that the role of *stakeholder* very high to increase the number of tourist visits.

Other Support Services

Other supporting services are services from the local community or management that are offered to tourists to complement tourism needs in the Sekawan Sejati area.

Table 7: Criteria for Other Supporting Services Indicators

No	Criteria	Strongly Disagree		Don't agree		Agree		Strongly agree		Total	
		Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%
1	Perception of availability of public transportation for tourism	1	5	5	24	12	57	3	14	21	100
2	Perception of food and beverage service providers	2	10	5	24	12	57	2	10	21	100
3	Perception of digital payment availability	0	0	5	24	14	67	2	10	21	100
4	Perception of tour guide knowledge	1	5	1	5	16	76	3	14	21	100
5	Perception of tour guide services	1	5	3	14	15	71	2	10	21	100
6	Perception is not provided atm	2	10	7	33	11	52	1	5	21	100

Source, primary data 2024

Based on Table 9, other supporting services in ecotourism management in Sekawan Sejati support ecotourism development through education about tourist attractions to tourists, providing them with an understanding of the environment that needs to be protected in accordance with applicable forest management policies. This aligns with Achmadi's research *et al* (2020) that ecotourism development requires management related to the development of services that involve cultural and environmental awareness for tourists.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that:

1. Ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area is based on regulations from the West Lombok Tourism Office, the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH), the Nuraksa Nature Reserve (Tahura Nuraksa), the Village-Owned Enterprises (Bumdes), and the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis). The management aspects at Sekawan Sejati include:

a. Attraction (70% Agree)

Attractions are tourist attractions visited by tourists and a source of income for the Sekawan Sejati community. The area boasts natural, man-made, and cultural attractions that have been clearly licensed by the government, thus requiring official entrance tickets.

b. Human Resources (62% Agree)

Human resources are the potential that can be developed to manage the tourism potential in Sekawan Sejati. The people in the Sekawan Sejati area possess excellent Indonesian language skills, enabling them to interact with tourists, and their hospitality is recognized for providing a sense of security to visitors.

c. Institutional (67% Agree)

Institutions are social systems that strive to achieve the goals of managing the Sekawan Sejati ecotourism area. The Sekawan Sejati area is managed by Village-Owned Enterprises (Bumdes) and Tourism Groups (Pokdarwis), in collaboration with the West Lombok Tourism Office, the West Rinjani Forest Management Unit (KPH), and the Nuraksa Nature Reserve (Tahura Nuraksa) to maintain the tourism infrastructure and facilities in Sekawan Sejati.

d. Other Support Services (67% Agree)

Other supporting services include businesses that provide various tourism needs in the Sekawan Sejati area. Other supporting services in ecotourism management in the Sekawan Sejati area support ecotourism development by educating tourists about tourist attractions and providing them with an understanding of the environment that needs to be protected in accordance with applicable forest management policies.

THANK-YOU NOTE

The author would like to express his gratitude to the National Aznas of West Lombok Regency for funding this research in 2025. Furthermore, he would like to thank the Environment and Forestry Service of NTB Province, the West Lombok Regency Government, the West Lombok Regency Tourism Service, and the Sekawasan Sekawan Sejati tourism management who have supported and assisted in the implementation of this research.

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